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PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 25

Issue 5

Pages: 659-666

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2380

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13822883

Manuscript Accepted: 08-18-2024

Management Support to MAPEH Program Implementation and Teachers' Competency: Basis of a Proposed Action Plan

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the management support of school administrators to the MAPEH program implementation and its relationship to the teachers' competency in selected public secondary schools of Pasig City during the school year 2023-2024 to serve as a basis for development of an action plan. The study used the descriptive-survey method of research as it was deemed most appropriate to use in determining the status of the MAPEH program in terms of its implementation as well as the status of the MAPEH teachers' competency. Based on the findings, the management support of school administrators to the MAPEH program implementation was to a high level. In addition, the MAPEH teachers' level of competency was assessed as very high by the two groups of respondents. Furthermore, there was a significant relationship between the level of management support to the MAPEH program implementation and the teachers' level of competency. There was a significant relationship between the level of management support to the MAPEH program implementation and the teachers' level of competency.

Keywords: *management support, teachers' competency, MAPEH, action plan*

Introduction

Education is a dynamic field that continually evolves to meet the diverse needs of students in an ever-changing society. Further, in the dynamic landscape of education, the importance of a holistic approach to student development has come to the forefront. Beyond the realm of traditional academic subjects, Music, Arts, Physical Education, and Health (MAPEH) have emerged as integral components of a well-rounded education, fostering creativity, physical well-being, and a comprehensive understanding of the human experience (Silvestre, 2020).

The important place of MAPEH in the curriculum is reflected in DECS Order No. 11, series 1989 otherwise known as the implementation of the New Secondary Education Curriculum (NSEC) under the 1989 Secondary Education Program (SEDP) which stated that the curriculum includes eight subject areas including Physical Education, Health and Music.

DepEd Order No.8 Series 2015 highlights the four subjects that constitute the MAPEH which are the Music, Arts, Physical Education and Health that should be taught both in the elementary and secondary level.

Thus, MAPEH encompasses a diverse range of subjects, each contributing to the holistic development of students. Music, with its power to evoke emotions, nurture creativity, and enhance cognitive skills, plays a vital role in shaping students' artistic expression and self-discovery. Arts education, encompassing visual arts, dance, and theater, cultivates imagination, critical thinking, and the ability to communicate and interpret the world through various artistic mediums. Physical education, promoting physical fitness, motor skills development, and overall health, lays the foundation for a healthy lifestyle and well-being. Health education, imparting knowledge about personal health, hygiene, and disease prevention, empowers students to make informed decisions about their physical and mental well-being (De Vera, 2017).

Indeed, the effective Implementation of MAPEH requires a supportive school environment that recognizes the value of these subjects and provides the necessary resources and encouragement for their successful integration into the curriculum. School management plays a crucial role in creating such an environment, providing leadership, guidance and support to MAPEH teachers and ensuring that these subjects are given due importance in the overall educational experience.

Further, school management plays a central role in shaping the school's culture and climate, which in turn influences teaching and learning. Effective school management can create a supportive and enriching environment that promotes the successful implementation of curricula. Adequate instructional resources, including facilities, equipment, supplies and materials in addition to the professional development opportunities are essential for effective curriculum implementation.

However, in the course of implementation of the MAPEH program, some serious problems have cropped up such as inadequate facilities, incompetent MAPEH teachers and poor supervision of the program. As revealed in the study of Veloso (2019), the MAPEH teachers expressed that their school heads, although supportive in the undertaking of MAPEH activities, failed to provide their schools with the basic facilities and equipment especially in teaching physical education. His study further revealed that most of the MAPEH teachers have no specialization or are not major on any of the MAPEH subjects.

The foregoing problems are also being encountered in other schools including that of the present researcher. The MAPEH teachers find difficulty in teaching the four components of the program due to lack of facilities, equipment and teaching materials. Also, not all MAPEH teachers are adequately prepared to teach the subject due to lack of specialization, thus, are wanting of trainings to enhance

their knowledge and skills.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the management support of school administrators to the MAPEH program implementation and the teachers' competency in selected public secondary schools of Pasig City during the school year 2023-2024 to serve as a basis for development of a training program. More specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of management support to the MAPEH program implementation as perceived by the teacher respondents and the school administrators in terms of the following variables?
 - 1.1. Provision of instructional resources;
 - 1.2. Professional development of teachers;
 - 1.3. Upgrading of facilities; and
 - 1.4. Supervision
2. Is there a significant difference in the perceptions of the two groups of respondents on the school administrators' level of management support to the MAPEH program implementation in terms of the aforementioned variables?
3. What is the level of competency of MAPEH teachers as assessed by the school administrators and the teachers themselves in terms of the following aspects?
 - 3.1. Classroom management;
 - 3.2. Mastery of MAPEH subject;
 - 3.3. Lesson delivery; and
 - 3.4. Assessment of learning
4. Is there a significant difference between the assessments of the two groups of respondents on the MAPEH teachers' level of competency in terms of the aforementioned aspects?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the level of management support to the MAPEH program implementation and the MAPEH teachers' level of competency?
6. Based on the findings of the study, what action plan maybe proposed?

Literature Review

One of the salient features of the K-12 curriculum is the teaching of the subject, Music, Arts, Physical Education and Health (MAPEH). It is taught to the learners both in the elementary and secondary level with different content standards and learning competencies as reflected in DepEd Order No.8, series 2015. It seeks to expose and develop students' appreciation for Philippine Asian and Western Music (Silvestre, 2020).

The importance of MAPEH as a subject was articulated by several authors and researchers. De Vera (2017) highlighted the value of MAPEH based on her reviewed literature when she stated that MAPEH contributes to cognitive function and improves the performance of the learners in mathematics, languages, arts and other academic subjects which all lead to developing creativity. She also cited an article that gives the value of music and physical education.

According to Cunliffe (2023), instructional leaders like the school principals can support curriculum implementation in six ways as follows; a) reground in the instructional vision, b) define role within the instructional implementation, c) consider different professional learning structures, d) internalization and practice and assessing current practice, e) define one's metrics and f) celebrate growth and success.

On the other hand, Espino (2017) described a competent MAPEH teacher as having the ability, knowledge and skill in in teaching the subject to make sure that the students can learn will learn and has learned about the subject. She further described MAPEH teaches as dynamic who create a balance in the development of the learners.

Cancio (2019) conducted a study to determine the implementation of MAPEH curriculum in selected public secondary schools in San Juan District, Division of Batangas. The findings of the study disclosed the areas that needed attention like inadequate trainings and workshops among MAPEH teachers, poor participation of parents and community leaders in the school activities, inadequate P.E activities and time allotment that hampered students' development of physical and sports competencies and inadequate regular communication and coordination with parents and community leaders.

Meanwhile, a study that focused on MAPEH teachers was conducted by Buedron (2016). The finding revealed that non-MAPEH majors were rated by both the students and department heads as low in terms of knowledge and skills in teaching physical education.

Another study that focused on MAPEH teachers' competency was undertaken by Itaas et al. (2020) wherein the researcher determined the competency level of MAPEH teachers in teaching Performing Arts based on K-12 curriculum in secondary public schools. It revealed that the MAPEH teachers were highly competent in using assessment data, monitoring students' data and achievement, using ICT resources for the teaching-learning process, giving feedback, making good use of allotted time and employing design.

On the other hand, Parrocha (2022), for instance, conducted a study to find out the challenges faced by primary school principals in

curriculum management. The findings revealed that principals try to fulfill their roles and responsibilities as curriculum leaders but face some challenges such as lack of knowledge, resources, low motivation of teachers and a large workload among others.

Furthermore, Govindasamy and Labrado (2022) disclosed that principals were not directly involved in the facilitation of curriculum changes but delegated it to their deputy principals and department heads. Thus, the researchers recommended that the school principals should make a paradigm shift by placing high priority to the procurement of adequate resources, providing support and professional development to the teachers and keeping abreast with latest trends in teaching.

Methodology

Research Design

The study used the descriptive method of research since it was most appropriate to use in determining the present condition of the MAPEH program in terms of its implementation as well as the teachers' level of competency. As De Belen (2015) states, "descriptive research is a method that seeks and describes something out there such as the status, condition or experience of a subject." Specifically, the study used the descriptive-correlational method of research since it tried to find out if significant relationship exists between the two main variables of the study- the level of management support to the MAPEH program implementation and the teachers' level of competency. As Garcia (2017) states that correlational research seeks to find out whether a relationship exists between two quantifiable variables. It also seeks to describe the existing relationship between variables, hence, is classified as a form of descriptive research.

Respondents

The data in this study were obtained from the 19 school administrators and 45 MAPEH teachers from public secondary schools in Clusters, Division of Pasig City. The respondents were selected through census survey since all the administrators and the MAPEH teachers in their respective schools were included in the study. Table I shows the distribution of respondents by school.

Instrument

The main instrument used in the study was a survey-questionnaire in a checklist form. Initially, it was prepared by the researcher in consultation with his adviser. After improving the developed questionnaire based on the comments and suggestions of his thesis adviser, the researcher prepared the second draft of his research instrument. Then, the researcher subjected his research instrument to validation of the three selected experts composed of two graduate professors and one MAPEH supervisor. After the validation process, the developed survey-questionnaire was finalized for administration to the respondents.

Procedure

To gather the needed data of the study, the researcher first sought permission through a formal letter from the Schools Division Office of Pasig City to allow him to administer his questionnaires. After having sought the necessary approval, the researcher also sought permission from the principal of each school involved in the study for the administration of his questionnaire to the intended respondents. The researcher personally administered the survey-questionnaire to the respondents of his study. Likewise, he also personally retrieved the same from the respondents to be able to get a high percentage of return.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher observed the necessary ethics in the conduct of his study. He first informed the respondents regarding the involvement in the study and got their consent. He also explained to the respondents that their participation is voluntary and their responses to the questionnaire will be treated with outmost confidentiality and anonymity.

Results and Discussion

Level of Management Support to the MAPEH Program Implementation

Table 1. *Level of Management Support to MAPEH Program Implementation In Terms of Provision of Instructional Resources*

Indicators	Teachers		School Administrators	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. Makes an assessment of the MAPEH program's instructional needs.	4.04	H	4.39	H
2. Allocates the necessary budget for instructional purposes.	3.80	H	4.44	H
3. Purchases and provides adequate equipment, supplies and materials needed for MAPEH subjects.	3.64	H	4.22	H
4. Provides adequate digital learning resources such as computer, laptop, televisions, etc. for teachers' and students' needs.	4.15	H	4.44	H
5. Solicits assistance of stakeholders in providing the MAPEH program's learning needs.	3.82	H	4.00	H
	Average Weighted Mean		3.90	H

The table shows that both the teachers and school administrators perceived the level of management support to the MAPEH program implementation as high as revealed by the average weighted mean of 3.90 and 4.30, respectively. As a whole, the findings show that the management of the respondents' schools support the MAPEH program implementation to a high extent. Thus, the finding implies that the implementation of the MAPEH program in the schools of the respondents is enhanced through provision of instructional resources.

The findings of the study were supported by the article of Cunliffe (2023) which emphasized the vital role of the management in the implementation of a curricular program. According to the author, instructional leaders like the school principals are the main responsible and pursuing to support curriculum implementation in the school in many ways all through out for the whole year of school days.

Table 2. *Level of Management Support to MAPEH Program Implementation In Terms of Professional Development of Teachers*

Indicators	Teachers		School Administrators	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. Makes regular training need assessment of MAPEH teachers.	3.85	H	4.44	H
2. Plans and develops professional development program for MAPEH teachers.	4.04	H	4.50	VH
3. Conducts continuous re-tooling trainings for non-MAPEH majors.	3.64	H	4.47	H
4. Provides re-skilling and up-skilling seminars/trainings for MAPEH teachers.	3.83	H	4.44	H
5. Encourages the teachers to pursue advance studies.	4.30	H	4.72	VH
Average Weighted Mean	3.92	H	4.51	VH

The data reveal that the MAPEH teachers perceived as high the level of management support to the teachers' professional development as shown by the average weighted mean of 3.92, while the school administrators perceived the level of management support as very high as shown by the average weighted mean of 4.51. The finding implies that the school administrators find the need for the MAPEH teachers to enhance their instructional knowledge and skills through advance studies, hence, encourage them to pursue a master's degree program or post graduate program and finished master's degree.

This finding is supported by the study of Culajara (2021) which disclosed that MAPEH teachers had limited seminars, workshops and trainings attended which it is really needed for the professional growth of the MAPEH teachers in order to enhance more the teaching strategies to the students.

Table 3. *Level of Management Support to MAPEH Program Implementation In Terms of Upgrading of Facilities*

Indicators	Teachers		School Administrators	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. Conducts regular assessment of the condition of MAPEH physical facilities.	3.85	H	4.39	H
2. Develops a plan and program for physical facilities improvement.	3.98	H	4.39	H
3. Allocates budget for provision of needed facilities to conduct MAPEH activities.	3.77	H	4.44	H
4. Provides the needed facilities for MAPEH classes such as storage rooms for sports equipment and musical instrument.	3.64	H	4.17	H
5. Creates a maintenance committee to do necessary repair and refurbishment of MAPEH facilities.	3.67	H	4.31	H
Average Weighted Mean	3.78	H	4.35	H

The data disclose that both the teachers and the school administrators perceived that the management support to the MAPEH program implementation was to a high level as shown by the average weighted mean of 3.78 and 4.35, respectively. The finding implies that efforts are made by the management in the schools of the respondents to upgrade MAPEH facilities. However, there is still a room for improvement since the highest weighted mean was not obtained for the MAPEH facilities.

The aforementioned challenge finds support in the study of Dulay (2022) which revealed that storage rooms for equipment are lacking as well as other challenges like inadequate facilities, incompetence of some MAPEH teachers in teaching all the components of the subject, limited students' engagement in MAPEH activities and difficulty of MAPEH teachers in carrying out online instruction for students' activities.

As reflected in the table, the level of management support to the MAPEH program implementation was high as revealed by the average weighted mean of 3.97 from the teachers and 4.32 from the school administrators. The findings imply that there is a need for more improvement in making regular report on the status of MAPEH as well on assignment of utility workers for maintenance of school cleanliness.

Thus, the findings also imply the importance of supervision for successful implementation of the MAPEH program and this was emphasized by Elbanna (2021) when she stated that one of the objectives of supervision is to improve teachers' skills. She further stated that the supervisor has a duty to assist the teachers in staying up to date with new trends and pedagogical approaches.

Table 4. *Level of Management Support to MAPEH Program Implementation In Terms of Supervision*

Indicators	Teachers		School Administrators	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. Conducts regular observations and monitoring of MAPEH program implementation.	4.19	H	4.44	H
2. Sees to it that the instructional equipment is available and adequate.	3.96	H	4.50	VH
3. Assigns utility workers/personnel to maintain the cleanliness of MAPEH facilities.	3.81	H	3.94	H
4. Makes a regular report on the status of MAPEH facilities and instructional resources.	3.79	H	4.28	H
5. Conducts evaluation of MAPEH program implementation and submit a report to concerned authorities.	4.11	H	4.44	H
Average Weighted Mean	3.97	H	4.32	H

Test of Significant Difference in the Perceptions of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Level of Management Support to the MAPEH Program Implementation

Table 5. *Test of Significant Difference in the Perceptions of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Level of Management Support to the MAPEH Program Implementation*

Variables	t-value	p-value	INT	Decision
1. Provision of instructional resources	2.13	0.037	S	Reject Ho
2. Professional development of teachers	3.37	0.001	S	Reject Ho
3. Upgrading of facilities	2.69	0.009	S	Reject Ho
4. Supervision	1.86	0.066	NS	Fail to reject Ho

The finding thus implies that the school administrators and the MAPEH teachers should collaborate and coordinate with one another in the planning and execution of MAPEH activities so they will have similar perspective on how the MAPEH program can best be implemented. The finding also suggests both the school administrators and the MAPEH teachers should give attention to the different aspects of MAPEH program implementation such as provision of instructional resources, professional development of teachers, upgrading of facilities and supervision.

Level of Competency of MAPEH Teachers

Table 6. *Level of Competency of MAPEH Teachers In Terms of Classroom Management*

Indicators	Teachers		School Administrators	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. Keep clean and orderly classroom including its furniture before teaching.	4.66	VH	4.50	VH
2. Plan and design appropriate instructional tasks for the learners.	4.58	VH	4.61	VH
3. Set and explain clearly class rules and procedures before the class starts.	4.74	VH	4.61	VH
4. Use variety of effective teaching strategies and techniques to stimulate the students' interest in the lessons.	4.60	VH	4.61	VH
5. Engage the students in learning through provision of group activities, problem set, seat works, etc.	4.58	VH	4.67	VH
6. Manage classes effectively using appropriate strategies to maintain proper students' discipline and behavior	4.15	H	4.44	H
Average Weighted Mean	4.60	VH	4.60	VH

As shown in the table, both the teachers and the school administrators assessed the level of MAPEH teacher's competency as very high with similar average weighted mean of 4.60. The finding implies that there is a need for improvement on the use of effective strategies to properly discipline the students. The finding is supported by the study of Bilasa (2016) which disclosed that the MAPEH teachers should have trainings and seminars in the use of appropriate teaching strategies among others especially to the academic status of the learners.

Table 7. *Level of Competency of MAPEH Teachers In Terms of Mastery of Subject*

Indicators	Teachers		School Administrators	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. Have sound knowledge of subject matter, hence, teach without reading notes.	4.45	H	4.56	VH
2. Provide varied examples and applications to lead student to higher order thinking.	4.47	H	4.56	VH
3. Relate content with other related or allied areas or disciplines	4.74	VH	4.61	VH
4. Synthesize the discussed lessons to highlight the main points for easy understanding	4.47	H	4.39	H
5. Clarify very well the misconceptions of students about the lessons/topics.	4.56	VH	4.56	VH
6. Give accurate answers to student questions.	4.58	VH	4.65	VH
Average Weighted Mean	4.51	VH	4.54	VH

The data reveal that both the teachers and the school administrators assessed the level of MAPEH teachers' competency as regards mastery of subject as very high with an average weighted mean of 4.51 and 4.54, respectively. The finding implies that the MAPEH teachers are confident in transmitting their knowledge of the lessons or topics since they know what to teach as they perform their instructional tasks.

The finding is parallel to that of the study of Buedron (2016) in which the MAPEH teachers were rated as low in terms of knowledge and skills in teaching.

Table 8. Level of Competency of MAPEH Teachers In Terms of Lesson Delivery

Indicators	Teachers		School Administrators	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. Use instructional strategies that make students participate lively in the learning process.	4.54	VH	4.56	VH
2. Use questioning techniques that stimulate students' thinking and motivate them to pay attention.	4.52	VH	4.44	H
3. Use appropriate instructional materials that facilitate students' understanding of lessons.	4.61	VH	4.50	VH
4. Select and pace learning activities that sustain students' interest.	4.37	H	4.44	H
5. Explain difficult concepts using simple terms.	4.43	H	4.56	VH
6. Use verbal and non-verbal language to stimulate and maintain student interest.	4.46	H	4.44	H
Average Weighted Mean	4.49	H	4.49	H

As can be gleaned from the table, the level of competency of MAPEH teachers in lesson delivery was assessed as high by the teachers with an average weighted mean of 4.49 and similar rating by the school administrators.

The findings show that the two groups of respondents perceived the MAPEH teachers as skillful in the use of teaching strategies as well as in the use of right teaching materials to help their students understand well their lessons.

Table 9. Level of Competency of MAPEH Teachers In Terms of Assessment of Learning

Indicators	Teachers		School Administrators	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. Plan and prepare different assessment tools.	4.39	VI	4.59	VI
2. Use different assessment strategies such as question-answer, portfolio, etc.	4.37	H	4.56	VH
3. Monitors students' performance.	4.57	VH	4.72	VH
4. Provide useful feedback to assist students in their performance.	4.43	H	4.44	H
5. Conduct authentic assessments such as interview, demonstration/ performance, oral presentations, group projects, etc.	4.43	H	4.50	VH
6. Utilizes test result for instructional improvement.	4.43	H	4.56	VH
Average Weighted Mean	4.44	H	4.56	VH

The table shows that the level of competency of the MAPEH teachers in terms of assessment of learning was assessed as high by the teachers with an average weighted mean of 4.44. The school administrators, meanwhile, assessed the same item as very high as shown by the average weighted mean of 4.56.

The finding implies that the MAPEH teachers are passionate with their profession almost that are really doing their job well by giving their responsibility and dedication to teach all throughout to teaches the students in order to learn and to grow and most especially in monitoring the academic performance of their students from first quarter to fourth quarter of school year period.

Test of Significant Difference in the Assessment of the Two Groups of Respondents on the MAPEH Teachers' Level of Competency

Table 10. Test of Significant Difference in the Assessment of the Two Groups of Respondents on MAPEH Teachers' Level of Competency

Variables	t-value	p-value	INT	Decision
1. Classroom Management	0.01	0.993	NS	Fails to reject Ho
2. Mastery of the Subject	0.19	0.850	NS	Fails to reject Ho
3. Lesson Delivery	0.01	0.992	NS	Fails to reject Ho
4. Assessment of Learning	0.89	0.376	NS	Fails to reject Ho

The table shows that there was no significant difference between the assessment of the two groups of respondents on the MAPEH teachers' level of competency as revealed by p-value greater than 0.05 level of significance for classroom management, mastery of the subject, lesson delivery and assessment of learning. Thus, the test of significant difference failed to reject the hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the assessment of the two groups of respondents on the MAPEH teachers' level of competency. The finding

implies that both groups of respondents had similar perspective on the teachers' level of teaching competency. In addition, school administrator and MAPEH teachers are intact to each other in terms of level of competency in teaching process that will deliver to the students for the successful of their academic status.

Test of Significant Relationship Between the Level of Management Support to the MAPEH Program Implementation and the MAPEH Teachers' Level of Competency

Table 11. *Test of Significant Relationship Between Management Support to the MAPEH Program Implementation and the MAPEH Teachers Competency*

	Management Support/ Teachers' Level of Competency	Pearson R	t-value	p-value	INT	Decision
1.	Classroom Management	0.407	3.56	0.000	S	Reject Ho
2.	Mastery of the Subject	0.553	5.30	0.000	S	Reject Ho
3.	Lesson Delivery	0.494	4.55	0.000	S	Reject Ho
4.	Assessment of Learning	0.530	4.96	0.000	S	Reject Ho

As reflected in the table, there was a significant relationship between the level of management support to the MAPEH program implementation and the MAPEH teachers' level of competency as shown by p-values lesser than 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis there is no significant relationship between the two main variables of the study was rejected. The finding implies that the management support is very crucial in the successful implementation of the MAPEH program.

Proposed Action Plan for Enhancement of Management Support to the MAPEH Program Implementation

Rationale

There are some areas that require considerable attention and improvement in the MAPEH program. One area that needs improvement is the lack of adequate resources, specifically, facilities, equipment, supplies and materials for effective teaching of the MAPEH subject. Another pressing issue is the need for continuous training of MAPEH teachers wherein retooling, re-skilling and upskilling have to be afforded to them. Facing the challenge of keeping up with global standards will provide the students with more specialized skills and better prepare them for higher education or employment.

Addressing the foregoing issues is best facilitated with the support of the school management. The success of any academic or curriculum program lies greatly on the leadership of the school head. In particular, the successful implementation of the MAPEH program can be realized through the close supervision, monitoring and improvement action of the school management and the collaboration of the MAPEH teachers engaging in professional development like attending seminars and training that benefited them individually on their profession. Hence, an action plan is deemed imperative and is hereby proposed.

Objective

The action plan hereby proposed aims to:

Guide the school administrators on what particular areas of the MAPEH program need to be given attention and action.

Highlight the areas that require planning for further improvement.

Provide the strategies and activities to be undertaken to effectively implement the MAPEH program.

Encourage school administrators to fully sustain the implementation of the MAPEH program.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, the following are the conclusions drawn from the results of the study.

The management in the schools used as subjects of the study provide the needed assistance for the implementation of the MAPEH program to a certain extent.

The MAPEH teachers possess the needed knowledge and skills for effective teaching of MAPEH subjects.

The management support to the MAPEH program implementation has bearing on the MAPEH teachers' level of competency.

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